
A STUDY ON FACTORS DRIVING INDIAN STUDENTS' CHOICE BETWEEN STUDYING ABROAD AND PURSUING HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA AMIDST EVOLVING GLOBAL EDUCATION TRENDS**¹Prajakta Bapat, ^{2*}Nandana Jalesh, ^{3*}Nisha Rana, ^{4*}Sakshi Sable, and ^{5*}Vanshika Singh**

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ABSTRACT

Due to the fast amounts of globalization taking place today, students from India are making choices based on the type of place they want to attend as they consider both the international hubs that are well-known globally and the changing college system in India. This is a qualitative and quantitative study of the changing way that students are choosing schools based on the way they are being affected by Global Economic Barriers, including the costs of tuition; in addition to their ability to obtain visas to leave India to attend schools abroad. This is a study of the "Return on Investment" of a degree obtained in India compared to a degree obtained abroad. This study also looks at whether or not the "Gold Standard" of an international education continues to be at the forefront of education or if the line between Local Education and Global Education is starting to fade.

KEYWORDS: Higher education, international mobility, NEP 2020, student preferences, India, Return on Investment (ROI).

INTRODUCTION

The process of globalization has made a significant impact on the decision-making process of individuals, in reference to higher education, Indian students in particular, and decisions on where to study, i.e., in India or any other country. Based on research infrastructure and reputation, the US, UK, Canada, Australia, and Germany are perceived to offer better institutions of higher education by students globally. However, due to global economic pressures and changes resulting from national policy initiatives, such as India's National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, domestic institutions have been strengthened, and there are now more globally aligned educational opportunities within India. Because of these factors, students need to take a more strategic approach to evaluate their options in light of their expected return on investment (ROI), rising costs of tuition and living abroad, visa restrictions, and more competitive alternatives of education in India.

The study aims to analyze the changing perceptions in the Indian Students regarding the interest in pursuing higher education abroad or in India, and to evaluate whether the desire to study abroad continues to be the preferred educational path, compared to the growing and developing competitive options available in India.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

In today's globalized society, Indian students are faced with a difficult choice about whether to pursue further education in India or to study overseas. Although many perceive foreign universities to provide better academic quality, exposure to worldwide culture, or they provide more employment opportunities, they also require more financial investments, impose strict visa regulations, and necessitate significant cultural changes on the part of the student. Simultaneously, reforms like the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 in India have improved the academic standard and recognition of higher education institutions in India. Therefore, these developing trends will leave Indian students uncertain about what the most appropriate location is when deciding where to pursue higher education because of the many different factors that influence students' decisions.

OBJECTIVES

1. To identify the key factors affecting the choices of Indian students regarding studying abroad vs continuing their higher studies in India.
2. To analyze the changing preferences of Indian students regarding favored study locations abroad and the emerging alternatives in India.
3. To assess the effect of international education trends (cost, quality, visa regulations).
4. To evaluate challenges and opportunities encountered by the students both abroad and domestic.

NEED OF THE STUDY

The rising costs of international education and the growing quality of Indian institutions make it important to examine the changes that are occurring within the global educational trends that influence students' decision-making. Therefore, this study aims to understand the factors influencing Indian students' choice between studying abroad and pursuing higher education in India amidst evolving global education trends.

HYPOTHESIS

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant correlation between perceived quality of education and student decisions regarding whether to study abroad or to pursue an advanced degree in India.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant correlation between perceived quality of education and student decisions regarding whether to study abroad or pursue an advanced degree in India.

LIMITATIONS

1. The application of convenience sampling has caused a loss of random selection and a possible bias in the study.
2. Geographic concentration has created a lack of representation from certain Indian states.
3. There is limited representation across social class and academic backgrounds.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. **Primary Data:** A structured questionnaire (Google Form) with closed-ended questions was created to collect primary data.
2. **Sampling Technique:** A survey of 100 individuals, primarily undergraduate students and young professionals, who are deciding on future education was conducted using a convenience sampling method.
3. **Data analysis method:** Descriptive statistics (including percentages, tables, graphs) were used to analyse the data and identify patterns in students' preferences for studying in India or abroad.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. **Ranim Chaya (2025)**, highlighted German college programs are steadily rising and are now ranked among India's most desired places for college education, while traditional UK and US universities are in decline. Student's preferences have shifted toward sites that have consistent visa stability and post-graduation job availability.
2. **Khushbu Agarwal (2021)**, conducted a doctoral study at ICFAI University in Jharkhand. Important determinants were identified in the decision to study abroad such as: the lack of quality educational institutions in India; better employment opportunities in a global market; and internationally recognized credentials. The influence of the parent(s), friendship network and family income played a role in determining where to attend school. However, the two biggest impediments for students were large financial obligations (costs) and issues surrounding the required visas to study in another country.
3. **Mazzarol, T., & Soutar, G. N. (2002)**. study reveals that to develop a model of the push and pull factors affecting the decision-making process for choosing an international study destination they identified the following push factors as potential contributors to an international student's choice of destination country: dissatisfaction with the quality of education provided in one's home country; limited options for study (e.g., program choice); and limited access to postsecondary programs due to competitive admission processes. Pull factors considered in the model as positively influencing an international student's choice of destination include: the reputation of the host institution; the recognition of academic qualifications received from the host institution; safety and security of the host country; cost of living; and policies related to obtaining a student visa.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

- 81% of the sample population consists of participants aged 18 to 23, showing that most of them are younger undergrad students who are currently preparing to pursue their future degree options.
- 41% of students are third-year students, while 22% are professionals that have graduated, which shows the majority of people are very close to deciding upon where to continue their study or to enter their field of work.
- Students from commerce, management and technical have the most representation with the fields BBA (23%), B. Com (12%), BMS (12%), BTech (12%) and MBA (11%) being the most populated within the sampled group.
- 50% of the surveyed have expressed their desire to study in India; 34% would prefer to study abroad, while 16% were uncertain, resulting in an overwhelming trend toward domestic education.

- 60% of respondents rated the quality of education that they would receive from a foreign country as a rating of 4 or 5 on a standard scale, indicating that most would perceive the academics of foreign countries to be greater than the academics of the institutions in India.
- 48% of those surveyed cited being near family and 32% of respondents cited financial savings (lower tuition and/or living expense) as being the two major factors of choice they would prefer to stay in India, being defined as having an emotional and financial reason.
- High finances and living expenses (61%) ranked as the highest are identified as the biggest challenges to studying abroad, indicating that financial concerns play a major role in students’ international education decisions.

- 40% of those surveyed indicated their major reasons for studying outside of India were due to having better job opportunities internationally, with their next choice being the prestige/networking internationally (27%) and then the quality of education (18%).
- 38% of the respondents chose Top Indian Institutes as the most preferred destination, followed by Australia and Canada. This indicates a stronger preference for pursuing higher education in India, although some students still show interest in studying in major international destinations.
- In terms of how much these factors impact their decision to study abroad; the majority of respondents gave a moderate to high rating (3 or 4) to indicate that rising costs of living abroad and increasing standards of education in India are both causing them to consider studying in India versus studying abroad.
- Results regarding questions related to visa requirements and hybrid learning were primarily in the neutral to moderate range (3), indicating that while they impact their view about studying in India, they are not main determining factors by any means.
- Most respondents gave a rating of 2 or 3 when asked if they believe that opportunities for internships and employment in India are of the same caliber as what they would get from a foreign institution. This suggests that while many students prefer pursuing their education in India, they still perceive the quality of internship and employment opportunities to be stronger abroad.

- This data illustrates that Indian students have a more balanced view about an international education versus an Indian education than previously thought, as many Indian students perceive that studying abroad provides them with the opportunity to gain an additional level of global experience and job opportunity, but that studying in India has become a reasonable, competitive and affordable option for many students.

INFERENCE ANALYSIS

Table 1: Perceived superiority of abroad education vs actual preference

Indicator	Percentage
Agree Abroad Education is Superior	60%
Prefer Studying Abroad	34%
Prefer Studying in India	50%

Approximately, 60% of respondents believe international education to be of better quality than domestic but only 34% of those will actually pursue an international education. This suggests that perception of quality does not correlate to preferred destination. There may be a number of other factors that outweigh perceived distance.

Table 2: Cost factor & appeal of Indian education

Indicator	Percentage
Agree Lower Cost Makes India Preferable	50%
Identify High Finances as Biggest Abroad Challenge	61%

Finances are of primary importance in the decision-making process for students. The increasing cost of tuition & living outside of the country seems to be a primary reason behind students selecting an Indian institution over a foreign institution.

Table 3: Global career advantage vs actual abroad choice

Indicator	Percentage
Better Global Job Opportunities as Main Pull	40%
International Networks/Prestige as Pull	27%
Prefer Abroad Overall	34%

Although many factors seem to have a positive impact on global careers or global connections, only a very small percentage actually select to attend school abroad. Therefore, there seems to be a disconnect from what the students aspire to do and what they actually end up doing.

Table 4: Growth of Indian institutions and reduce in abroad pull

Indicator	Percentage
Agree IITs/IIMs Gaining Preference	43%
Agree Improving Indian Rankings Reduce Abroad Pull	42%
Prefer India as Top Destination	50%

Students recognize the improving quality and global outlook of Indian Institutions, and the growing number of reputed Indian Institutions contributes to their growing preference for studying in India.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this research report demonstrates that although education from abroad remains highly regarded as of high academic quality and world-class, Indian students are making decisions about where to go to school based on practical issues in addition to educational issues; these practical issues include affordability/length of the visa process, distance from home, ROI, and the increasing quality of Indian Institutions. Therefore, the student preference for choosing between studying in India or studying abroad are gradually changing as the acceptance of higher-education institutions within India increases compared to the institutions outside of India. According to the primary data, the rising cost of studying abroad and the improving quality of Indian Institutions are influencing more students to pursue their higher education in India. However, the secondary data sources indicate that many students still prefer studying abroad due to the perceived academic and career advantages offered by the foreign institutions.

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